

TITLE” INTEGRATING BIOTECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS AND PLANT GENETIC RESOURCES FOR SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. The Agriculture Modernization Project, funded by the World Bank since August 2020, aims to enhance agricultural productivity and promote high-value horticulture value chains. The project comprises four key components: strengthening agricultural services, investing in high-value horticulture, facilitating trade and marketing, and ensuring effective project management and evaluation. To support these objectives, the project is strategically investing in the upgrade of the Plant Genetic Resource Institute to enhance its capabilities and ensure it meets contemporary agricultural challenges. This initiative focuses on the integration of advanced technologies and biotechnological innovations, including marker-assisted selection, modern genetic technologies, to accelerate the development of resilient and high-yield crop varieties which are stored in Uzbek Genebank. Key equipment will include high-throughput genotyping systems, gene manipulation tools, modern greenhouses, winter gardens, modern farm machinery, and water-saving technologies, along with state-of-the-art breeding facilities that support speed breeding techniques. Additionally, the project will support the repairing and upgrading of the existing genebank to enhance its capacity for preserving and managing plant genetic resources having more than 40 000 accessions of 100 agricultural crops. The main goals of this investment is to improve the efficiency of plant breeding processes, enhance the genetic diversity of crops, and ultimately increase food security. As a result of these interventions it is expected that institute will rapidly develop climate-resilient cultivar for local farmers, and a strengthened capacity for research and development in plant genetics. These interventions also include national and international training programs for the institute's staff, equipping them to effectively utilize the new equipment and effectively utilize technologies to achieve their objectives. These modernization effort will position the institute as a leader in sustainable agricultural innovation, contributing significantly to the resilience of the agricultural sector in the face of climate change and evolving food demands.